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Table 2. Features of Jaldi Dhan (JD) showing tolerance for moisture stress, New Delhi, India. 1989 WS.

Variety	Stressed					Nonstressed control		
	Initial		Terminal			Harvest index	Grain yield (t/ha)	Grain yield/d (kg/ha)
	Drought score ^a	Recovery score ^b	Spikelet fertility (%)	Relative water content (%)	Grain yield (% of nonstressed control)			
JD1	2	2	52.0	62.5	58	.38	3.2	52.0
JD3	3	3	45.5	58.0	50	.40	3.5	54.0
JD6	2	2	54.0	62.0	52	.44	3.4	54.0
JD8	2	3	50.8	61.5	48	.38	3.0	45.0
Dular (traditional check)	2	3	50.0	57.5	30	.30	2.0	23.0
Cauvery (semidwarf check)	8	5	0.0	30.5	0	.45	4.0	42.0

^a1 = least affected, 9 = most affected. ^b1 = maximum recovery, 9 = minimum recovery.

Seed technology

Seed technology for cold tolerance in rice

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Most indica rices exhibit susceptibility to cold stress at seedling stage, which causes slow or staggered seedling growth and delayed maturation. As a result, fields remain occupied longer, causing late sowing of the subsequent crop. We developed a simple technique to overcome the constraints of cold susceptibility of rice seedlings.

Rice seeds of cultivar CBI were incubated (for pretreatment) on moist germination paper at 4 °C for 0 (control), 1, 2, 3, and 5 d. Untreated (0 d) and pretreated sets (20 seeds/set) were then germinated at 18 ± 2 °C on a germination plate. One hundred seeds were sown in earthen pots under field conditions (15–23 °C) to assess the ability of the seeds to adapt to cold conditions at the seedling stage. The experiment was repeated three times, maintaining a constant water volume. Root and shoot lengths were measured after 5 d of incubation on germination plates and above soil shoot length (in pots) was measured after 17 d (Fig. 1).

To determine the rate of cellular activity during germination under cold stress, we estimated the incorporation of ³⁵S-methionine in untreated and cold-pretreated seeds. Seeds were imbibed in water for 0–22 h at 18 ± 2 °C. Germinating embryos were then excised and

1. Root and shoot lengths of seedlings being assessed for cold tolerance.

incubated in germinating medium (sterile 3% sucrose) + ³⁵S-methionine for 22–24 h at 18 ± 2 °C. The embryos were then homogenized in Tris-HCl buffer (pH 7.5). To this homogenate, an equal volume of 10% trichloroacetic acid (TCA) was added and the precipitate was collected in a GF/A filter. The filtrate was washed and dried and incorporation counts in the precipitate were estimated in a liquid scintillation counter using PPO and POPOP as scintillants and toluene as a solvent.

2. Incorporation of ³⁵S-methionine (sp.act. 200 ci/mmol; 50 µl) into TCA insoluble material in rice embryos.^a

^a³⁵S-methionine counting efficiency of 90–95%; counts were taken at SE of 2%. Bar indicates the standard deviation of the mean (SDM) of repeated experiments.

Cold-pretreated seeds behave differently with different durations of exposure to cold temperatures. Under cold stress in both the laboratory and the field, the 1-d

pretreated seeds exhibited significantly higher root/shoot growth and emergence above soil compared with the control and other pretreated sets. This improved

seedling growth was associated with significantly higher protein synthesis ability during early hours (22-24 h) of germination under cold stress. ■

Crop and resource management

Fertilizer management

Potassium fertilizer for higher yields in scented rice

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The area under scented rice varieties is growing because of the premium price they command compared with that of high-yielding nonscented varieties. The fertilizer recommendation for nonscented varieties is high (150, 26.4, 49.8 kg NPK/ha) compared with scented varieties (60 kg N/ha and 13.2 kg P/ha for tall, and 90 kg N/ha and 13.2 kg P/ha for dwarf). High N fertilizer doses lead to lodging of scented rices, whereas K enhances the plant's resistance against lodging. Applying K is not recommended for these varieties.

We conducted a field study to compare the responses of three scented rices (HB1, HBC19, Basmati 370) at four fertility levels: 60-13.2-0, 60-13.2-24.9, 60-13.2-49.8, and 90-19.8-37.3 kg NPK/ha. Thirty-five-d-old seedlings (2/hill) were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing. All of the P and K was applied before transplanting and the N in two equal splits at 21 and 42 d after transplanting. The grain yield and yield components were recorded at harvesting. Plants were harvested and then dried for 3 d before threshing. Grain yield was recorded at about 16% moisture.

Effect of fertility levels^a on yield and yield components of some scented rices. RRS, India.

^a1 = 60-13.2-0 kg NPK/ha, 2 = 60-13.2-24.9 kg NPK/ha, 3 = 60-13.2-49.8 kg NPK/ha, 4 = 90-19.8-37.3 kg NPK/ha.

